

THE COMPARISON OF GRAMMATICALLY SIGNIFICANT VERB CLASSIFICATIONS BETWEEN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Abstract: The article discusses the problem of verb categorization in the English and Uzbek languages, recommending a classification based on vocabulary and grammar relationships. Provides a wide range of examples with explanations in three, English, Russian and Uzbek languages.

Keywords: 10.5281/zenodo.6482318 As you know, the role of the verb in the formation of a sentence (statement) is great. One of the important problems associated with verbs is its classification and there are different points of view on this.

From the point of view of participation-non-participation of the grammatical meaning, the classification of the verb can be: 1) lexical-semantic; 2) lexicogrammatical; 3) grammatical.

Lexico-semantic classification (semantic fields, lexical-semantic groups, thematic groups, series, antonymic pairs) are mainly carried out in lexicology.

For grammar, in that view, lexico-grammatical and grammatical classification of the verb are important. The lexico-grammatical classification of the verb is based on the relationship between vocabulary and grammar. The largest and most comprehensive lexico-grammatical classification in a language is the parts of speech. The lexical aspect of parts of speech consists in abstract categorical meanings, such as actions, objects, features, etc., expressed by the stem or root of the verb. The grammatical aspect is grammatical meanings expressed by morphological categories (time, modality, voice, person, number, etc.).

The basis of grammatical classification is only a grammatical feature. An example of this is the division of English verbs into standard and non-standard types.

Lexico-grammatical and grammatical classifications of the verb play an important role in the study and teaching of a foreign language, in the description of the grammatical structure of the language. They represent a grammatically relevant (meaningful) classification of the verb.

According to the authors, grammatically relevant classifications should be included in textbooks and manuals on the grammar of a foreign language. After analyzing the literature, it was revealed that the classification of verbs is given differently in different sources. There are even some grammar books that do not deal with the classification of verbs at all.

Based on our research, we concluded that the following grammatically relevant types of verbs exist in English and Uzbek.

1. Types of verbs based on dependence and independence of meaning

According to their meaning and the role performed in the sentence, verbs in both languages are divided into significant and structural.

The lexical meaning of significant verbs is complete and they are expressed independently. Nominative verbs are usually a member of a sentence, and they are given in Uzbek and English dictionaries without a marker. Significant verbs are an open system. The nomination of an event cannot be imagined without significant verbs, because they denote specific actions, processes, states of substances in the objective world and are an important part of the nomination.

Structural verbs cannot express meaning on their own, they cannot play the role of a member of a sentence. They mainly serve as significant verbs, are usually used to express grammatical meaning, help the main verb express modality, aspect, tense, voice, negation, taxis and other grammatical meanings. An important grammatical feature of structural verbs lies precisely in this.

In English, structural verbs are divided into linking verbs, auxiliary and modal verbs, and in Uzbek into linking verbs, auxiliary and auxiliary (кўмакчи) verbs.

Link verbs (Link Verbs) together with a noun, adjective or numeral form a compound nominal predicate. They connect the predicate (nominal part of the predicate) expressed by a noun, adjective or numeral with the subject.

In English, they are divided into true linking verbs (to be) and special linking verbs (look, seem, appear, feel, taste, become, get, grow, remain, keep, turn).

Some structural verbs of the Uzbek language (эди, эмиш, экан, бўлмоқ), depending on the context, can be connective (Мен касал эдим. - I was sick.) and auxiliary verbs (У ҳам борган эди. - He was also there.)

Auxiliary verbs in English are to do, to have, to be, shall, will, should, would. They serve to form grammatical forms: Do you speak English? He has come. In the Uzbek language, when the verbs эди, эмиш, экан and бўлмоқ function as an auxiliary verb, they form verb forms: У кетаётган эди - (He leaves).

Service verbs (кўмакчи) exist in the Uzbek language and are a stumbling block in Turkic studies and in Uzbek linguistics. Their meaning, use and other qualities were studied by A. Gulyamov [4] and A. Khozhiev [5].

Service verbs (кўмакчи), depending on their meaning, can form analytical forms of the verb or derivative verbs. If they completely lose their lexical meaning, the nominative verb and the service verb (кўмакчи) can be considered as an analytical form, if they partially lose their lexical meaning, then they cannot be classified as a derived verb. Service verbs (кўмакчи) include the following verbs: бошламоқ (start), ётмоқ (lie down), турмоқ (stand up), юрмоқ (walk), ўтирмоқ (sit), бўлмоқ (be), битирмоқ (finish), олмоқ (take), бермоқ (give), қолмоқ (stay), қўймоқ (put), чиқмоқ (leave), бормоқ (go), келмоқ (come), кетмоқ (leave), юбормоқ (send), ташламоқ (quit), солмоқ (put), тушмоқ (to go down), ўлмоқ (to die), ўтмоқ (to pass), етмоқ (to get there), кўрмоқ (to see), қарамоқ (to look), боқмоқ (to look), ёзмоқ (to write) [6].

It should be noted that in English the functions of Uzbek service verbs (кўмакчи) are performed by adverbs, which are called by some linguists post positives (up, out, in, down, on, off and others): to cut up, to cut out, to cut in, to cut down, to cut on, to cut off.

Modal verbs exist in English: can, must, may, should, ought to, shall, will. They differ in their form, grammatical features, meanings, uses and a number of other features and serve to express such modal meanings as the possibility, probability, necessity, desirability of performing an action, as well as expressing emotions, surprise and pity. Apart from can (could) and may (might), modal verbs do not have any grammatical category. None of them has the form of the infinitive, gerund and gerund; auxiliary verbs do not participate in the formation of the negative form, only the particle not is added. Therefore, they are considered insufficient verbs (Defective Verbs). Modal verbs in combination with the infinitive of the semantic verb serve as a compound verbal predicate in the sentence.

As can be seen from the features of significant and structural verbs, such a division of verbs is carried out on the basis of lexical and grammatical features.

2. Классификация глаголов по способу образования формы:

Стандартные глаголы (существуют в обоих языках)

В узбекском языке все глагольные формы образуется на основе определённых правил. У ишлади. (Он работал.) В английском языке прошедшее неопределённое время стандартного глагола (Past Indefinite Tense) и причастие прошедшего времени (Past Participle) образуется путем прибавления к форме инфинитива окончания –ed. He worked.

Нестандартные глаголы (существует в английском языке)

Нестандартные глаголы не образуются путем прибавления окончания –ed к инфинитиву, а различными другими способами — путем изменения гласных и согласных звуков (rise-rose; send-sent), путем изменения корня (go-went) и без изменения формы (put-put). He came at 2 o'clock. A broken pen.

Количество нестандартных глаголов невелико, они представляют закрытую систему и отображаются в словарях и учебниках. Большинство глаголов являются стандартными глаголами. Нестандартные глаголы являются непродуктивными. В настоящее время не образуются новые нестандартные глаголы.

3. Types of verbs in terms of their relationship to the object:

Transitive verbs (exist in both languages): The action indicated by transitive verbs is directed towards an object. He is reading a book. — У китоб ўқияпти. (Он читает книгу).

Intransitive verbs (exist in both languages): The action indicated by intransitive verbs is not directed at an object. He is sleeping. — У ухлаяпти. (Он спит)

Mixed Verbs (Bifunctional) (exists in English): In English, the same verb can be used contextually or distributively as either a transitive or an intransitive verb: They sell books. (They sell books) - transitional the books sell well. (Books sell well) - intransitive.

An analysis of the English explanatory dictionary “OALD” showed that there are 1475 such verbs in this dictionary. In the dictionary, this kind of verb is marked as (vi; vt).

Unfortunately, mixed verbs are not mentioned in any English grammar textbook. Learners of English use mixed verbs only as transitive verbs. In our opinion, a list of mixed verbs should be given in English grammar textbooks.

4. Types of verbs according to obligatory valency:

The appearance of the subject and objects in the sentence depends on the valency of the verb. The verb, by its valence, opens vacancies to the subject and objects. In linguistics, the requirement for the presence of a subject and additions (actants) by a verb is called obligatory valency. According to obligatory valency, verbs are divided into the following:

Monovalent verbs (exist in both languages): Monovalent verbs are intransitive, they open a vacancy for the subject (first actant) only. Nick works. – Ник ишлайди. (Nick works)

Bivalent verbs (exist in both languages): Bivalent verbs are transitive verbs and they open a vacancy for the subject (first actant) and direct object (second actant). Nick called her. – Ник уни чақирди. (Nick called her). Trivalent verbs (exist in both languages):

Trivalent verbs are also a kind of transitive verbs, they open vacancies for the subject (the first actant) and two objects (the second third actant) - direct and indirect object. Nick gave me some money. – Ник менга пул берди. (Nick gave me money).

In some languages, for example, in Russian, there are aivalent (non-valent) verbs: darken (Darkens), evening (Darkens). Such verbs do not open a vacancy for either the subject or the object. There are no such verbs in English and Uzbek.

According to the authors, on the basis of linguistic and speech dichotomies, the valency of the verb should be considered both in terms of language and in terms of speech. Valency of verbs in a language (linguistic valence of a verb) is the ability of a verb to open potential vacancies for the subject and objects, as well as information in the verb about the possibility of filling these vacancies with nouns with certain semantics. Valency of a verb in speech (speech valency of a verb) is the realization of linguistic valency in speech, i.e. filling potential vacancies with nouns with a specific semantic and specific form. In this case, the predicate agrees with the subject in person and number, and the additions must be in the right case or used with certain prepositions or must be in certain syntactic positions. Valence in different languages differs mainly in speech.

5. Types of verbs requiring a prepositional object:

a) Verbs that require a prepositional object (exists in English): to listen to, rely on / upon, to accuse of, to consist of, to depend upon / on, to complain about, to object to and others.

b) Verbs that require an unprepositional object (exists in English): to read, to cut, to send, etc.

In the Uzbek language, the same types of verbs can also exist. For example, a verb that requires an object in the original case: овқатдан лаззатланмоқ (enjoy food). However, this issue needs separate research.

6. Verbs requiring a formal subject: Such verbs exist only in English, but do not exist in Uzbek. The number of these verbs is counted and they express atmospheric phenomena, to rain, to snow, to drizzle, to hail. It is raining. (It's raining). In such sentences, 'it' is considered the formal subject.

7. Verbs used with semi-predicative syntactic constructions (exists in English): Some semantic types of English verbs have a grammatical feature. For example, semi-predicative syntactic constructions The Objective-with-the Infinitive Construction, The Objective-with-the-Participle Construction, The Subjective Infinitive Construction, The Subjective-with-the-Participle Construction are used with the verbs of sight, hearing, touch and mental or causative verbs (to get, to have, to make).

8. Intransitive verbs used in the passive voice (exists in the Uzbek language): in the Uzbek language, some intransitive verbs expressing human actions, unlike English transitive verbs, can be used both in the active and in the passive voice (бормоқ - in the active voice; борилмоқ - in the passive voice).

9. Types of verbs in terms of limiting the action by time (exist in both languages): Terminative and non-terminal verbs. There are such verbs in both languages, but in English they are grammatically relevant. Compare: Мен уни кўрмаймман. (in extended form); I don't see him. (in an extended form).

10. Types of verbs according to the ability to express predications:

Predicative verbs (exist in both languages): He works — У ишлайди.

Non-predicative verbs exist in both languages, but their types overlap.

Infinitive (exist in both languages): to write, to speak — ёзмоқ (to write), гапирмоқ (to speak). The English infinitive, unlike the Uzbek one, has a much broader range of functions. In the modern Uzbek language, action names are used instead of the infinitive.

Gerund (exists in English): writing (писание), speaking (говорящий), helping (помощь).

Participle (exist in both languages): written, spoken — ёзган, гапираётган. There are more participial phrases in Uzbek than in English.

A gerund (деепричастие) (exists in the Uzbek language): ёзиб, ёза (wrote), гапириб, гапира (speaking).

And so, in grammar, when classifying a verb, one should proceed from the connection between grammar and vocabulary. Of the 26

grammatically relevant verb types, 15 exist in both languages, 8 only in English, 3 only in Uzbek. Some of the similar types of the verb differ in the degree of grammatical relevance, meanings, forms and uses.

References

1. Blokh, M.A. Course in Theoretical English Grammar / M.A. Blokh. – Moscow: Vysshaya shkola, 1983. – 383p.
2. Gulyamov, A.G. The Verb / A.G. Gulyamov. – Tashkent, 1954. – 88 p.
3. Karaulov, Yu. N. General and Russian Ideography / Yu.N. Karaulov. – Moscow, 1976. – 354 p.
4. Khozhiev, A. The Verb / A. Khozhiev. – Tashkent: Nauka, 1973. – 192 p.
5. Khozhiev, A. Auxiliary Verbs in Uzbek / A. Khozhiev. – Tashkent: Nauka, 1966.v–v221p.
6. Shchur, G.S. The Field Theory in Linguistics / G.S. Shchur. – Moscow, 1974. – 120 p.
7. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/grammaticheski-relevantnye-klassifikatsii-glagola-angliyskogo-i-uzbekskogo-yazykov/>
8. Ochilov, A. (2012). Education and economic growth in Uzbekistan. *Perspectives of Innovations, Economics and Business, PIEB*, 12(3), 21-33.
9. Ochilov, A. (2014). Is higher education a driving force of economic growth in Uzbekistan?. *Perspectives of Innovations, Economics and Business, PIEB*, 14(4), 160-174.
10. Ochilov, A. O. (2017). The Higher Education Dynamics and Economic Growth: The Case of Uzbekistan. *Journal of Management Value & Ethics*, 7(2), 46-53.
11. Ochilov, A. O. HIGHER EDUCATION IS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN STIMULATING ECONOMIC GROWTH. *GWALIOR MANAGEMENT ACADEMY*, 23, 133.
12. Khashimova, N. A. (2017). Methodical issues of formation and estimation of investment climate. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*. Rochester. United Kingdom, 5(4), 560-566.
13. Khashimova, N. A., & Tursunkhodjaev, M. L. (2020). DEVELOPMENT OF CHANNELS OF INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL MOVEMENT IN THE SYSTEM OF INNOVATIVE COOPERATION IN EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND PRODUCTION. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(9), 3348-3355.
14. Abitovna, H. N., Tillaeva, B., & Razzakova, B. The Essence of the Investment Potential and Patterns of the Investment Fields in the Economy.

15. Odilovich, O. A., Fayzullaevich, K. G., Djuraevna, R. M., Bakhtiyorovich, K. S., & Narkulovich, D. O. (2020). Suggestions For Improving The Efficiency Of Management Of Training Highly Qualified Personnel In The Higher Education System Of Uzbekistan. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(3), 3687-3695.

16. Очиллов, А. О., & Шадиёв, Т. (2015). Проблемы современной системы высшего образования в Узбекистане и пути их решения. *Северный регион: наука, образование, культура*, (1), 19-24.

17. Odilovich, O. A., Sharifa, G., Lola, B., Komila, A., & Zarifa, M. (2021). Higher education as a factor in increasing economic growth in Uzbekistan. *Psychology and Education Journal*, 58(2), 5006-5013.

18. Очиллов, А. О. (2012). Инновационное развитие высшего образования в Узбекистане. *Экономическое возрождение России*, (2 (32)), 193-196.

19. Ochilov, A. O. (2019). PROPOSALS ON MODERNIZATION OF THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *Economics and Innovative Technologies*, 2019(4), 14.

20. Очиллов, А. О. (2020). МЕТОДИЧЕСКОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ЖИЗНЕДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ. In *ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ* (pp. 48-51).

21. Odilovich, O. A., & Najjibullah, E. (2021). How to Reduce Poverty in Afghanistan. *Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability*, 577-581.

22. Ochilov, A. O., & Najjibullah, E. (2021, April). HOW TO REDUCE POVERTY IN AFGHANISTAN. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 114-117).

23. Хашимова, Н. А. к. э. н. ТГТУ РАЗРАБОТКА ТЕОРИИ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА И МЕХАНИЗМОВ ЕГО ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ В УСЛОВИЯХ МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ ЭКОНОМИКИ.

24. Khashimova, N., & Norov, A. (2020). Synergetic development of investment processes. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 9(2), 5818-5820.

25. Abitovna, H. N., & Buranova, M. A. Ensuring Employment of the Population is a Pledge of Effective Use of the Labor Potential of the Country.

26. Khashimova, N., & Khusanjanova, J. (2016). Generation of investment potential. *Voice of Research*, 5(1), 46-48.

27. Abitovna, H. N., Abdukadirovna, B. M., & Marina, A. Priority areas for the development of investment potential of Uzbekistan.

28. Хашимова, Н. А. к. э. н., доц. ТГТУ МЕХАНИЗМА ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА: СУЩНОСТЬ И ПРИНЦИПЫ ПОСТРОЕНИЯ.

29. Khashimova, N., Tillaeva, B., & Razzakova, B. (2020). Essence of investment potential and patterns of investment fields in the economy. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 9(2), 5853-5855.

30. Jurakulovna J.G., Bahodirovich R.U. Improving the Theoretical Framework of Internal Audit in the Corporate Governance System//*Middle European Scientific Bulletin* 19, -2021. С.345-348.

31. Jurakulovna J. G. The Necessity and Theoretical Basis of Financial Statement Analysis in Modern Management // *Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability*. – 2021. – Т. 7. – С. 89-95.

32. Jurakulovna J. G., Iskandarovich R. R. Theoretical and Methodological Fundamentals of Economic Analysis in Management of the Modern Economy // *Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability*. – 2021. – С. 304-310.

33. Очиллов, А. О., & Левкина, В. С. (2016). ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТАМОЖЕННОГО СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА В РАМКАХ ЕВРАЗИЙСКОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО СОЮЗА. In *ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ* (pp. 14-18).

34. Узаков, Н. У., Абдиев, А. Ч., Раимова, М. Д., & Очиллов, А. О. (2014). НЕЗАВИСИМОСТЬ И УСКОРЕНИЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ. In *ФЕНОМЕН РЫНОЧНОГО ХОЗЯЙСТВА: ОТ ИСТОКОВ ДО НАШИХ ДНЕЙ* (pp. 372-375).

35. Очиллов, А. О., & Эргашев, Т. Ш. (2020). К вопросу о совершенствовании управления трудоустройством выпускников высших образовательных учреждений в Республике Узбекистан. *Проблемы современной экономики*, (3), 174-177.

36. Очиллов, А. О. (2020). ЗАДАЧИ И СУЩНОСТЬ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ. In *Материалы международного научного форума «Образование. Наука. Культура»* (pp. 365-366).

37. Элмуродов, Н. С., Очиллов, А. О., & Элмуродова, С. С. (2020). ИНТЕНСИФИКАЦИИ ОТВОДА ТЕПЛОТЫ ОХЛАЖДАЮЩЕЙ ПОВЕРХНОСТИ БАКОВ ТРАНСФОРМАТОРОВ. In *ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ* (pp. 76-82).

38. Очиллов, А. О., & Элмуродов, Н. С. (2021). ПОДГОТОВКА КАДРОВ ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ЖИЗНЕДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ. In *ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ* (pp. 53-56).

39. Очиллов, А. О., & Ганиева, Ш. А. (2021). БЕЗОПАСНОСТЬ ЖИЗНЕДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ. In *Научный форум: Инновационная наука* (pp. 10-13).